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Dynamic simulation of the shading cast by a wind farm on an adjacent photovoltaic plant

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ABSTRACT: The hybridization of several renewable energy power generation sources is a viable option that can improve the use of available resources and space. However, the coexistence of different technologies, with different requirements for operation, can lead to some challenges. In the case of hybridization between a wind farm and an adjacent solar photovoltaic (PV) power plant, the wind farm can cast dynamic and static shadows on the nearby PV generators. Simple hypotheses are often chosen for their conservative character, but they often turn out to be overly pessimistic and can result in worse results in the project economics. This study evaluates the shading losses impacting a hybrid wind/PV park in a sunny region with a novel advanced 3D shading simulation tool using dynamic visualization based on the power of modern GPUs (Graphic Processor Unit). The application of this method to a case study in a sunny region shows that, as a function of the approximation that is used to model the blades of the wind turbines, the resulting estimated shading losses can be far too pessimistic, or too optimistic. The study also provides guidance on how to assess the possible existing tradeoffs between PV power installation density and shading losses, and how to apply it to the optimization of the layout of the PV plant.

Keywords: PV, simulation, shading, GPU, photovoltaic plant, wind farm

1. INTRODUCTION

The hybridization of several renewable energy power generation sources is a viable option that can improve the use of available resources and space. However, the coexistence of different technologies, with different requirements for operation, can lead to some challenges.

In the case of hybridization between a wind farm and an adjacent solar photovoltaic (PV) power plant[1], the wind farm can cast dynamic and static shadows on the nearby PV generators. Partial shading phenomena and their corresponding power losses on PV modules have been extensively studied [2]. However, these previous studies have generally dealt with fixed shading elements creating predictable shading that can be estimated over time. In the case of wind turbines, the rotation of long blades in the nearby area of the modules induces dynamic disturbances during short periods. Such disturbances can have a significant impact on the PV power generation, while being difficult to evaluate on a yearly basis.

The current state-of-the-art PV simulation tools cannot easily handle this kind of dynamic shading problems, hence simplified models are often used [3]. Depending on the simplifications chosen to evaluate the shading impacts, significant differences can be observed in the resulting dynamic shadow affected area. Simple hypotheses are often chosen for their conservative character, but they often turn out to be overly pessimistic and can result in unnecessarily reducing the energy production inputs of the project's financial model (Figure 1). Therefore, a more accurate and realistic approach is necessary.

This study evaluates the shading losses impacting a hybrid wind/PV park in a sunny region with a novel advanced 3D shading simulation tool using dynamic visualization based on the power of modern GPUs (Graphic Processor Unit).

2. POSSIBLE WIND BLADES MODELLING

Several possibilities exist to evaluate the energy losses associated with the shadows cast by the tower and blades of wind turbines on adjacent PV arrays. Wind generators are composed of two main elements: the tower and the rotating blades. Shading simulations need to account for these two shading sources. The shadows cast by the tower can easily be simulated because they are static, i.e., only affected by the sun's apparent movement, which is deterministic and relatively slow. On the contrary, the simulation of the blade-induced shading is much more complex because it requires dynamic modelling due to the nature of the movement of the blades. The blades are rotating around a horizontal axis (the hub of the turbine), and this rotation axis can change over time as a function of the dominant wind directions (the yaw mechanism within the tower). Several approaches are possible to evaluate the shading losses from the blades.

The most conservative approach is to assimilate the blades to an opaque sphere having the same diameter, thereby accounting for a large range of possible positions for these blades. This hypothesis does not require any knowledge of the dominant wind directions. The resulting shading is shown in Figure 1, where the heatmap represents the fraction of time, over one year, during which a specific area is shaded by the wind turbines. This leads to an overestimation of the shading losses that will affect the energy of the PV array because the wind turbine generators (WTGs) will not at any given time cast so much shadow on the array (the model works for all the possible wind directions, but at any given time the wind farm will experience a predominant wind).

Figure 1: Annual fraction of the time during which a specific area is shaded by a wind turbine, if the blades are assumed spherical.

The most frequent approach, used in standard wind turbine shadow modeling tools, is to approximate the blades to a disk, which is facing the predominant wind direction A illustrated in Figure 2.

This is a suitable approximation for windfarm sites which have a clear predominant wind direction. As with the previous assumption, this leads to an overestimation of the shading losses.

Figure 2: Shadows projected by a wind turbine on a PV array when assimilating the blades to a disk.

The resulting shading is shown in Figure 3. The results are far less conservative than with the spheric assumptions, but they are still relatively conservative because they assume a permanent shade over the array when in reality the 3 blades are a fast-moving dynamic shadow.

Figure 3: Annual fraction of the time that a specific area

is shaded by the wind generators, when assuming that the blades are disks.

A third approach that could be considered is to only take the central tower into account, without consideration for the blades. This obviously leads to an underestimation of the shaded area, as illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Shadows projected by a wind turbine on a PV array when only accounting for the central tower.

As shown in Figure 5, the result of this assumption is unsatisfactory because it is too optimistic and does not consider the impact of the moving blades.

Figure 5: Annual fraction of the time that a specific area is shaded by the wind turbines, when simulating shadows only for the central tower without blades.

The most realistic approach is to consider both the tower and the moving blades. The shadows that are cast at a specific moment by the tower and blades are illustrated in Figure 6. Both the static (no wind or other relevant turbine downtime) and dynamic movement of the blades need to be considered, which makes this case the most complex simulation case. Obtaining a fast and accurate solution for this problem is the object of this work.

Figure 6: Shadows cast at one moment by the tower and blades.

The resulting shading is illustrated in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Annual fraction of the time that a specific area is shaded by the wind turbines, when using a dynamic simulation for the movement of the blades.

3. METHODOLOGY

With current technology, virtually all computerized graphics systems are characterized by a special-purpose Graphics Processing Units (GPU). During the last decade, the performance of GPUs has surged, mainly driven by the ever-increasing demand emanating from the video game industry. Modern GPUs are very effective at manipulating computer graphics and image processing, and their highly parallel structure makes them more efficient than general-purpose Central Processing Units (CPUs) for algorithms that are designed to process large blocks of data in parallel [4]. The availability of powerful GPUs opens very promising possibilities for the simulation of complex 3D shading scenes applied to PV systems because the impacting shadows can be evaluated with a very high spatial resolution that reaches up to the PV cell level in short calculation times. The general problem of accurately evaluating shading losses based on GPU power has already been described in a previous work [5], and since then has been applied to numerous case studies for the solar industry.

In this work, a method is developed to account for the movement of the blades during the shading simulation, making use of specialized simulation libraries incorporated in GPUs. The simulations are carried out at temporal resolutions of typically 10-min or better. For each moment, an independent position of the blades is

associated to each one of the wind turbines surrounding the photovoltaic modules. The orientation of the plane of rotation of the blades is chosen so that it is representative, for each moment, of the dominant wind direction. The exact position of these blades is generated using a Monte-Carlo procedure, which provides a wide range of possible positions for the blade during the simulation period. This creates a set of blade positions that is statistically representative of reality in a one-year simulation period for a PV power plant, because a random distribution is applied over many time moments. It is worth mentioning that the wind resource at most windfarm site has high variability and the study did not focus on using wind data which was necessarily representative for the long-term conditions at the site as the purpose of this paper is to highlight the modelling approaches used.

For each moment in time, a geometric shading fraction is obtained at high spatial resolution, for each PV cell composing the PV array, as illustrated in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Visualization of the instantaneous shading caused by one wind turbine on a PV array.

This geometric shading is then converted into effective shading losses, using a diode equivalent model that allows to consider the electrical connection between the PV cells composing the PV modules and their bypass diodes [6]. The method considers the irradiance that is incident on each PV cell, as well as the electrical connection between these PV cells and the PV modules. The annual energy losses caused by shading are then estimated by integration of the shading losses calculated for each moment in time, and over the whole simulation period, typically using a Typical Meteorological Year (TMY) format [7]. This is illustrated in Figure 9.

The movements of the blade induce fast variations of the geometric factor on the PV arrays. The shadows typically appear and disappear in time fractions that are smaller than one second.

Figure 9: Integration of the shading fraction over a time period of one typical year for one wind turbine and one PV array.

4. CASE STUDY

The procedure described above is applied here to a real case study in which a PV plant with horizontal single-axis trackers (HSAT) is planned in the neighborhood of an already existing wind farm, located in a region with high irradiation. This section illustrates the main steps of the method when applied to a concrete project.

The annually integrated shading profiles of each wind turbine are obtained by weighting the geometric fraction at each time moment by the corresponding amount of solar irradiance. This produces a map of the effective shading losses on the ground and on the PV arrays, as illustrated in Figure 10 for the case of several wind turbines, and in Figure 11 for a closer view on one wind turbine, whose hub height is 150 meters and whose rotor diameter is 121 meters.

Figure 10: Cumulative shading effect over a one-year period on a large PV plant surrounded by several wind turbines.

Figure 11: Cumulative shading effect over a one-year period on a large PV plant surrounded by several wind turbines: Closer view on one wind turbine and the surrounding PV array.

A first study is carried out to determine the impact of the shadows cast by the wind turbines, taken one by one, as a function of their distance to the PV arrays. Figure 12 presents some illustrative comparison cases of effective shading losses from one wind turbine, with simulations considering only the tower (optimistic), the tower and a stationary disk (pessimistic), and the tower combined with a moving blade (realistic). The distance between the wind turbines and the PV arrays is taken along the east-west axis, and three subcases are represented: PV array in the same east-west alignment than the wind turbines, and PV array 50 meters north from one wind turbine, and PV array 50m south from the wind turbine. The simulation where the moving blades are assimilated to a disk translate into shading losses that are more conservative. The shading losses estimated with the tower only or with the moving blades are much lower than with the disk assumption.

Figure 12: Illustrative comparison cases of effective shading losses, with simulations considering only the tower (optimistic), the tower and a disk (conservative), and the tower combined with a moving blade (realistic).

The difference between the tower-only assumption and the dynamic model (moving blades) is visible in Figure 13, which presents a closer view of the shading losses in a range of values between 0% and 2%. The difference is particularly significant in the direction that is facing the dominant wind direction. In the case of this test case, the shading losses from the wind turbines are significant when the distance between the wind turbines and the PV arrays is less than 150 m, i.e. approximately the hub eight of the wind turbines.

Figure 13: Same as Figure 12, but showing a closer view of the shading losses in the range 0–2%.

In practice, one relevant question for the developer of the PV plant would be to determine the trade-off between the installed power density on the available land and the resulting shading losses from the wind turbines. When the turbines are sufficiently separated from one another, and when enough land is available between them for the installation of the PV arrays, it is possible to find areas where the shading losses are negligible. That part of the land can be advantageously occupied first. The PV arrays only need to be installed closer to the areas more affected by shading when the installed capacity needs to be increased, or when other constraints are in place. Therefore, beyond a certain installed capacity, significant shading losses might appear if the PV arrays are installed too close to the wind turbines. As a result, there is also a trade-off between the irradiation losses caused by turbine-induced shading and the irradiation losses caused by mutual shading of the PV modules, or their backtracking. If the pitch distance between the trackers is reduced, then it is possible to install more PV power in areas that are relatively unaffected by the wind turbines, at the cost of more backtracking losses. On the contrary, if the pitch distance is increased, then the backtracking losses decrease, but for the same installed power, the PV arrays need to be installed in areas that are more affected by shading from the wind turbines. For the present test case, Figure 14 shows the joint evolution of the total installed capacity the pitch distance between trackers, and the turbine-induced shading losses. In this test case, the most limiting factor in the total installable PV capacity is assumed to be the grid connection rather than the available land area. Therefore, it is possible to optimize the layout so that the turbine-induced shading losses are kept relatively low, i.e., under 1% for most of the PV arrays. However, this might not be always the case, for instance if the developer wishes to install more PV capacity on the same land area.

Figure 14: Joint evolution of the total installed power, the pitch distance between trackers, and the shading losses caused by the wind turbines.

In summary, for a given combination between the desired total installed capacity, the location and dimensions of the wind turbines, the nature and shape of the land, and other constraints, finding the optimum layout for the PV array requires a multi-parameter optimization. Such an optimization exercise of the layout is carried out here to exemplify the method further, and the resulting layout with the corresponding shading losses is shown in Figure 15.

Figure 15: Layout of the PV plant that results from the optimization of the trade-offs between installed power, shading losses from wind turbines, and backtracking losses. The annual shading losses (up to 2%) are shown with the color code to the right.

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

A novel method has been applied to the evaluation of the shading losses caused by the wind turbines on adjacent photovoltaic arrays. The application of this method to a case study in a sunny region shows that, as a function of the approximation that is used to model the blades of the wind turbines, the resulting estimated shading losses can be far too pessimistic, or too optimistic. The study also provides guidance on how to assess the possible existing tradeoffs between PV power installation density and shading losses, and how to apply it to the optimization of the layout of the PV plant.

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REFERENCES

- [1] S. Diaf, G. Notton, M. Belhamel, M. Haddadi, A. Louche, Design and techno-economical optimization for hybrid PV/wind system under various meteorological conditions, *Applied Energy*, 2008, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2008.02.012>.
- [2] A. Woyte, J. Nijs, R. Belmans, Partial shadowing of photovoltaic arrays with different system configurations: literature review and field test results, *Solar Energy*, Volume 74, Issue 3, 2003, Pages 217-233, ISSN 0038-092X, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0038-092X\(03\)00155-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0038-092X(03)00155-5).
- [3] PVsyst (<https://www.pvsyst.com/>).
- [4] D. Nehab, P.V. Sander, J. Lawrence, N. Tatarchuk, J.R. Isidoro, Accelerating Real-Time Shading with Reverse Reprojection Caching, 2007, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/1280094.1280098>
- [5] J. Robledo, J. Leloux, E. Lorenzo, C. A. Gueymard, From video games to solar energy: 3D shading simulation for PV using GPU. *Solar Energy*, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2019.09.041>.
- [6] F. Martínez-Moreno, J. Muñoz, E. Lorenzo, Experimental model to estimate shading losses on PV arrays, *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solmat.2010.07.029>.
- [7] S. Wilcox and W. Marion, Users Manual for TMY3, Data Sets, Technical Report, p. 58, 2008.